

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DEPENDENCE OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES ON PRIMARY HYPOTHYROIDISM

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Abstract

Currently, the close attention of scientists and practitioners is attracted to thyroid diseases associated with endemic foci of iodine deficiency in soil and water. Iodine deficiency diseases are among the most common non-infectious human diseases. Most often, pathology of the thyroid system is accompanied by hypothyroidism syndrome, caused by insufficient production of thyroid hormones and peripheral disturbances of their activity. One of the targets of endocrinological pathology is periodontal tissue.

Keywords: primary hypothyroidism, young people, periodontal disease.

The purpose of the study was to study the prevalence and intensity of periodontal tissue diseases in young people with primary hypothyroidism.

Results. According to the data obtained, periodontal diseases were detected in 78% of patients in group I with hypothyroidism. In persons without endocrine pathology, periodontal diseases were observed in 60% of the general population, which is 1.2 times less than the data of the 1st group. Intact periodontium in patients of the 1st group was found in only 12% of patients, while in the 2nd group there were twice as many patients with healthy periodontium. Generalized periodontitis of I and II degrees of development predominated in the structure of periodontal diseases. all age groups. Deterioration of the condition of periodontal tissues was observed in both Zvicom groups, but in patients with hypothyroidism, an increase in signs of early dystrophic-inflammatory periodontal lesions and rapid progression were studied. The relationship between the increase in intensity and generalization of the pathological process in periodontal tissues in young people and the duration of thyroid pathology.

Introduction. The number of organs and systems that respond to thyroid hormones includes the issue of thyroidology in the sphere of interests of various medical specialties, and the growing incidence of thyroid diseases in the population brings these problems to the forefront of modern endocrinology [1, 2]. Currently, close attention is paid to thyroid diseases, which are associated with endemic foci of iodine deficiency in soil and water [5]. Iodine deficiency diseases are the most common non-communicable diseases in humans [6, 8]. There are many areas in Ukraine where the population is at risk of iodine deficiency [4]. The absence or deficiency of iodine disrupts the synthesis of thyroid hormones, which leads to the development of hypothyroidism, one of the most common diseases of the endocrine system [3]. However, in the genesis of iodine deficiency diseases, the root cause of iodine deficiency is a weakening of the functional activity of the thyroid gland, which may be due not only to a reaction to iodine

deficiency, but also to the action of other stromogenic factors. factors. The decrease in the functionality of the thyroid gland increases under the influence of an unfavorable environmental situation, an increase in the number of stressors, and a busy rhythm of life. Most often, pathology of the thyroid system is accompanied by hypothyroidism syndrome, caused by insufficient production of thyroid hormones and peripheral disorders [7]. Most often, primary (thyroidogenic) hypothyroidism is caused by direct damage to the thyroid gland. The overall prevalence of primary manifest hypothyroidism in the population is 0.2–2%, subclinical – 7–10% among women and 2–3% among men [9]. With a deficiency of thyroid hormones, which are absolutely necessary for the normal functioning of almost every cell, weight gain develops in all organs and systems without exception. One of the manifestations of the influence of hypothyroidism on the body is damage to periodontal tissues. Methods - study of the prevalence and intensity of periodontal tissue diseases in young people with primary hypothyroidism.

290 people aged 25–44 years were examined. Of the total number of those examined, 174 people (60%) were diagnosed with primary hypothyroidism (group I). No endocrinological pathology was detected in 116 people (40%) examined; they made up group II.

Research results and discussion

According to the data obtained, 85.13±2.55% of young hypothyroidism patients had periodontal tissue disease, $p < 0.01$; in patients without endocrinological periodontal pathology, it was observed in 69.63±3.97% of those examined, which is 1.2 times less than the data of the 1st group. Intact periodontium was found only in 15% of patients in group I, whereas in patients in group II with healthy periodontium it was more common (30.37%). In the structure of periodontal diseases, generalized periodontitis of the initial 1st and 2nd stages of development predominated. Generalized periodontitis of the 3rd degree in patients of the 2nd group was detected only in 2.41±1.19% of people, while in the 2nd group there was no GP of the 3rd degree. This fact is

associated with the examination of young age groups of patients. Attention was drawn to the fact that earlier forms of periodontitis were detected in patients without endocrine pathology: there were 1.8 times more gingivitis than in patients with primary hypothyroidism (23.40 ± 4.39 and $12.65 \pm 2.59\%$, respectively); Localized periodontitis was detected in $21.28 \pm 4.24\%$ of patients in group II, while in patients in group I it was 1.9 times less common, $p < 0.01$ in terms of age. At the age of 25–29 years, periodontal diseases were detected in $73.58 \pm 6.11\%$ of those examined, which is 1.5 times more than in persons of the same age without endocrine pathology ($48.72 \pm 8.11\%$, $p < 0.01$). In the age range of 30–34 years, the percentage of periodontal diseases in patients with hypothyroidism increased to $85.33 \pm 4.11\%$, $p < 0.01$. An increase in the number of periodontal diseases was also observed in people of group II in a similar age group, but the percentage of people with periodontal diseases was significantly lower than in group I ($77.36 \pm 5.80\%$, $p < 0.01$). In the age range of 35–44 years, periodontal diseases were observed in patients with primary hypothyroidism in $94.03 \pm 2.92\%$ of those examined, and in patients without endocrinological pathology this figure was 1.2 times lower ($79.07 \pm 7.08\%$, $p < 0.01$). Thus, in patients with hypothyroidism, the prevalence and intensity of periodontal diseases is significantly higher than in persons without endocrine pathology in all age groups.

The condition of periodontal tissues of patients with primary hypothyroidism was analyzed depending on the duration of the underlying disease. According to the data obtained, it was established that in patients with endocrine pathology from 1 to 5 years, intact periodontium was found in $22.94 \pm 4.04\%$ of subjects, and the inflammatory process in the periodontium (gingivitis) was observed in 16, $51 \pm 3.57\%$ of persons and $60.55 \pm 6.01\%$ were diagnosed with periodontitis, $p < 0.01$. Total diseases of periodontal tissues in patients of group I with a duration of primary hypothyroidism from 1 to 5 years were observed in $77.06 \pm 4.19\%$ of cases, $p < 0.01$. With the duration of concomitant pathology, the number of people with healthy periodontitis decreased by 4.93 times, gingivitis was observed 4.73 times less often, and the number of dystrophic-inflammatory periodontal diseases reached $91.86 \pm 2.96\%$, which is 1.5 times more. data on persons with a history of hypothyroidism from 1 to 5 years, $p < 0.01$. The data obtained indicate an increase in the intensity and generalization of the pathological process in periodontal tissues in young people and an increase in the duration of endocrine pathology. As a result of the studies, the prevalence and intensity of periodontal disease were found to be significantly higher in patients with hypothyroidism at a young age compared to people without endocrine pathology at a young age. all age

groups. In the structure of periodontal tissue diseases, generalized periodontitis of I-I and II degrees of severity with a complicated course prevailed. With age, deterioration of the condition of periodontal tissues was observed in both groups, but in individuals with hypothyroidism, the increase in identified signs of early dystrophic-inflammatory periodontal damage and its rapid progression were studied. A relationship was revealed between the increase in intensity and generalization of the pathological process in periodontal tissues at a young age and the duration of endocrine pathology.

In further studies, it is planned to study changes in protein and mineral metabolism in sheep caviar homogenate using an experimental model of hypothyroidism and to substantiate the pathogenetic directions of corrected disorders.

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